

Optimal Strategy of Energy Aggregators in the Energy and Regulation markets: Chance-Constrained Approach

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Abstract—Multiple energy systems have become increasingly interdependent in recent years. In the smart grids, energy aggregators (EAs) as intermediaries between consumers and energy markets are responsible to supply the required energy of consumers. However, fluctuations in consumption could endanger the expected cost of EAs. Therefore, EAs shall use flexible resources to diminish the unexpected variation of demand. Among various types of energy resources, battery energy storages (BESs) and combined heat and power (CHP) units are flexible alternatives to provide the required electricity and heat demand of consumers. In this work, a linear model is presented for the participation of EAs in the energy and regulation markets based on the electrical and thermal requirements of consumers. To model the impacts of stochastic consumption, the chance-constrained programming approach is used. Moreover, the McCormick relaxation is addressed to linearize the cost function of the CHP unit. The performance is evaluated via a case study and various confidence levels. Simulation results indicate that increasing the confidence level from 0.75 to 0.85 results in a 5.4% increase in EA's costs.

Keywords— Battery energy storage, chance constrained programming, CHP, energy aggregator, McCormick relaxation.

NOMENCLATURE

A. Indices

t, T Index and set of time
 i, I Index and set of the category of consumers

B. Parameters

π^{DA} Day-ahead price (Euro/kWh)
 $\pi^{UR/DR}$ Up/down-regulation price (Euro/kWh)
 ρ^B Marginal cost of BES (Euro/kWh)
 P^L Electrical load of consumer (kW)
 $P^{CHP,A/B/C/D}$ Power coefficient of FOR curve (kW)
 $P^{CHP,min/max}$ Minimum/maximum electrical power of CHP unit (kW)
 $H^{CHP,A/B/C/D}$ Heat coefficient of FOR curve (kW)
 $H^{CHP,min/max}$ Minimum/maximum heat power of CHP unit (kW)
 a, b, c, d Coefficients of CHP cost function
 $\eta^{Ch/Dch}$ Charging/discharging efficiency of BES (%)
 $\bar{P}^{Ch/Dch}$ Maximum charging/discharging power of BES (kW)

$E^{min/max}$ Minimum/maximum energy capacity of BES (kWh)
 ξ Heat reduction coefficient (%)
 m Mass (kg)
 C^P Specific heat (Wh/kg·C)
 θ^{amb} Ambient temperature (C)
 $\theta^{max/min}$ Maximum/minimum temperature (C)
 $P^{+/-}$ Expected value of positive/negative variation of consumption (kW)
 $\sigma^{+/-}$ Standard deviation of positive/negative variation of consumption (kW)
 κ Confidence level

C. Variables

$P^{UR/DR}$ Purchased up/down-regulation power (kW)
 $P^{Ch/Dch}$ Total Charging/discharging power of BES (kW)
 $P^{Ch,DA/DR/UR}$ Charging power of BES in day-ahead/down-regulation/up-regulation planning (kW)
 $P^{Dch,DA/DR/UR}$ Discharging power of BES in day-ahead/down-regulation/up-regulation planning (kW)
 P^{CHP} Total Generated electricity of CHP unit (kW)
 $P^{CHP,DA/UR/DR}$ Generated electricity of CHP unit in day-ahead/down-regulation/up-regulation planning (kW)
 H^{CHP} Total Generated heat of CHP unit (kW)
 $H^{CHP,DA/UR/DR}$ Generated heat of CHP unit in day-ahead/down-regulation/up-regulation planning (kW)
 Z^{CHP} Auxiliary variable (kW)²
 $P^{+/-}$ Positive/negative variation of consumption (kW)
 v BES status binary variable (0: charging, 1: discharging)
 ν Commitment binary variable of CHP unit (0: off, 1: on)
 θ Temperature (C)
 E Energy of BES (kWh)

I. INTRODUCTION

Due to the high investment cost of large-scale power plants, environmental problems of fossil energy resources, and increasing the consumption of final consumers, using small-scale resources such as battery energy storage (BES), and combined heat and power (CHP) systems in distribution grids have been increased, significantly. Final consumers can give

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the responsibility of scheduling of resources to energy aggregators (EA). EAs can supply the required energy of their customers from the day-ahead and regulation markets or self-generating units. However, the uncertainty of consumption is inevitable. EAs can use flexible resources such as BESs and CHPs to compensate for the unexpected variations of demand. Accordingly, the main objective of this work is to present a model for EAs to determine their optimal energy trading strategy in the day-ahead and regulation markets as well as scheduling flexible resources.

The optimal strategy of aggregators and scheduling of distributed resources have been studied in various references. In [1], a linear model is proposed for scheduling BES and PV units in the local electricity and flexibility market. In the proposed model, impacts of uncertain parameters such as energy prices, PV generation, and consumption are studied. The optimal strategy of energy storage aggregators is studied in [2]. According to the presented results, using the flexible operation of energy storage could increase the profit of aggregators, significantly. In [3], a risk-based model is proposed for electrical vehicle aggregators. The optimal strategy of aggregators is determined in a way that maximizes the aggregator's profit and electric vehicle owners' comfort, simultaneously. In [4], a tri-level model is proposed for the participation of aggregators in the joint energy and reserve markets. In the upper and middle sub-problems, the optimal energy trading strategy of aggregators and maximizing the utility function of electric vehicle owners are studied. The uncertainty of availability of electric vehicles is modeled in the lower level sub-problem based on the worst-case scenario. The proposed model is converted to a single-level problem by the unimodularity property, primal and dual functions, and value function method. The impacts of demand response programs on the optimal strategy of aggregators are studied in [5]. The proposed robust model of [6] shows that utilizing the flexibility of electric vehicle aggregators decreases the operational cost of distribution companies. [7] provides a linear model for aggregators to provide the frequency control service by proper scheduling of vehicles and energy storage units. The interactions between aggregators and electric vehicles are investigated in [8]. In the presented model, the aggregation of electric vehicle reserve by aggregator and maximization of electric vehicle profits are modeled in the upper and lower-level problems.

Literature review shows that less attention has been paid to using the CHP units in the flexibility market. Dependency of the thermal and electrical performance of CHP units and thermal requirements of end-users is a challenge that shall be considered in the scheduling of these units in the flexibility market. In this work, a risk-based model is proposed for EA to schedule the CHP and BES units in order to decrease the fluctuations of consumption. In the proposed model, the chance-constrained optimization approach is used to handle the risk of uncertain consumption. Moreover, the McCormick relaxation method is used to linearize the performance function of CHP units.

The main contribution of this work can be summarized as follows:

- Aggregating the flexibility of household BES and CHP units in the optimal strategy of EA: In the proposed model, the BES and CHP units are used to diminish the uncertainty of consumption.

- Modeling the desired temperature of consumers in the optimal strategy of EA: In this work, the desired temperature of consumers is considered as a constraint in EA's scheduling problem. Accordingly, the optimal strategy of EA is specified in a way that supplies the required electricity and heat of consumers based on the minimum cost.
- Using McCormick relaxation approach: To linearize the cost function of CHP units, the McCormick relaxation approach as a fast and efficient solution is addressed in this work.

The rest of this paper is organized as follows: Section II provides the structure proposed problem. In Section III, the chance-constrained programming approach is introduced to evaluate the impacts of uncertain consumption. In Section IV, the performance and effectiveness of the model are evaluated via a case study. Conclusions are presented in Section V.

II. DETERMINISTIC SCHEDULING MODEL

In this paper, it is supposed that the required energy of the consumer can be supplied by BES, CHP, and the grid. Moreover, variations of demand can be compensated by the flexible resources (BES and CHP), and the regulation market. However, variation of CHP's electrical power could change the generated heat (and temperature) that should be considered in the scheduling of this resource. Hourly operational cost of EA to supply the demand of consumer i th is determined by (1).

$$C_{t,i} = \pi_{t,i}^{DA} \cdot P_{t,i}^{DA} + \pi_{t,i}^{UR} \cdot P_{t,i}^{UR} - \pi_{t,i}^{DR} \cdot P_{t,i}^{DR} + \rho_i^B \cdot (P_{t,i}^{Ch} + P_{t,i}^{Dch}) + C^{CHP}(P_{t,i}^{CHP}, H_{t,i}^{CHP}) : \forall t, i \quad (1a)$$

$$P_{t,i}^{DA}, P_{t,i}^{UR}, P_{t,i}^{DR}, P_{t,i}^{Ch}, P_{t,i}^{Dch}, P_{t,i}^{CHP}, H_{t,i}^{CHP} \geq 0 : \forall t, i \quad (1b)$$

In (1a), the first term represents the cost of purchasing from the day-ahead market. The cost of purchasing power from the up-regulation market and selling back power to the down-regulation market are represented by the second and third terms, respectively. The generation cost of BES and CHP units are calculated by the fourth and fifth terms, respectively.

$$P_{t,i}^{CHP} - \left(\frac{P_i^{CHP,B} - P_i^{CHP,A}}{H_i^{CHP,B}} \right) \cdot H_{t,i}^{CHP} \leq P_i^{CHP,A} : \forall i, t \quad (2a)$$

$$P_{t,i}^{CHP} - \left(\frac{P_i^{CHP,C} - P_i^{CHP,D}}{H_i^{CHP,C}} \right) \cdot H_{t,i}^{CHP} \geq P_i^{CHP,D} : \forall i, t \quad (2b)$$

$$(H_i^{CHP,B} - H_i^{CHP,C}) \cdot P_{t,i}^{CHP} \leq (P_i^{CHP,B} - P_i^{CHP,C}) \cdot H_{t,i}^{CHP} + P_i^{CHP,C} \cdot H_i^{CHP,B} - P_i^{CHP,B} \cdot H_i^{CHP,C} : \forall i, t \text{ if } \frac{P_i^{CHP,C}}{P_i^{CHP,B}} \leq \frac{H_i^{CHP,C}}{H_i^{CHP,B}} \quad (2c)$$

$$(H_i^{CHP,B} - H_i^{CHP,C}) \cdot P_{t,i}^{CHP} \geq (P_i^{CHP,B} - P_i^{CHP,C}) \cdot H_{t,i}^{CHP} + P_i^{CHP,C} \cdot H_i^{CHP,B} - P_i^{CHP,B} \cdot H_i^{CHP,C} : \forall i, t \text{ if } \frac{P_i^{CHP,C}}{P_i^{CHP,B}} > \frac{H_i^{CHP,C}}{H_i^{CHP,B}} \quad (2d)$$

Fig. 2. Convex feasible operational region of the CHP unit.

The convex feasible operational region (FOR) of the CHP unit is shown in Fig. 2 [15]. Accordingly, FOR is modeled by linear constraints (2). The cost function of the CHP unit is approximated by the quadratic function as follows:

$$C_{t,i}^{CHP} = a_i + b_i P_{t,i}^{CHP} + c_i H_{t,i}^{CHP} + d_i P_{t,i}^{CHP} H_{t,i}^{CHP} : \forall i, t \quad (3)$$

As mentioned before, the McCormick relaxation approach is a fast and efficient approach to linearize the bilinear terms. In the McCormick envelop optimization, the auxiliary variable Z is defined as follows:

$$Z_{t,i}^{CHP} = P_{t,i}^{CHP} H_{t,i}^{CHP} : \forall i, t \quad (4)$$

In this method, the auxiliary variable Z is approximated by linear estimators. Constraints (5a)-(5b) and (5c)-(5d) represent the under and over estimators, respectively.

$$Z_{t,i}^{CHP} \geq P_i^{CHP, \min} H_{t,i}^{CHP} + H_i^{CHP, \min} P_{t,i}^{CHP} - P_i^{CHP, \min} H_i^{CHP, \min} \quad (5a)$$

$$Z_{t,i}^{CHP} \geq P_i^{CHP, \max} H_{t,i}^{CHP} + H_i^{CHP, \max} P_{t,i}^{CHP} - P_i^{CHP, \max} H_i^{CHP, \max} \quad (5b)$$

$$Z_{t,i}^{CHP} \leq P_i^{CHP, \max} H_{t,i}^{CHP} + H_i^{CHP, \min} P_{t,i}^{CHP} - P_i^{CHP, \max} H_i^{CHP, \min} \quad (5c)$$

$$Z_{t,i}^{CHP} \leq H_i^{CHP, \max} P_{t,i}^{CHP} + P_i^{CHP, \min} H_{t,i}^{CHP} - P_i^{CHP, \min} H_i^{CHP, \max} \quad (5d)$$

The main operational constraints of EA's scheduling problem are:

1- The operation of BES in the day-ahead and regulation markets is limited by the maximum power capacity of batteries in charging and discharging modes, as follows:

$$P_{t,i}^{Ch} = P_{t,i}^{Ch, DA} + P_{t,i}^{Ch, DR} - P_{t,i}^{Ch, UR} : \forall i, t \quad (6a)$$

$$P_{t,i}^{Dch} = P_{t,i}^{Dch, DA} + P_{t,i}^{Dch, UR} - P_{t,i}^{Dch, DR} : \forall i, t \quad (6b)$$

$$0 \leq P_{t,i}^{Ch} \leq \bar{P}_i^{Ch} (1 - v_{t,i}) : \forall i, t \quad (6c)$$

$$0 \leq P_{t,i}^{Dch, DA} \leq \bar{P}_i^{Dch} (1 - v_{t,i}) : \forall i, t \quad (6d)$$

$$0 \leq P_{t,i}^{Ch, DR} \leq \bar{P}_i^{Ch} v_{t,i} : \forall i, t \quad (6e)$$

$$0 \leq P_{t,i}^{Ch, UR} \leq \bar{P}_i^{Ch} v_{t,i} : \forall i, t \quad (6f)$$

$$0 \leq P_{t,i}^{Dch} \leq \bar{P}_i^{Dch} v_{t,i} : \forall i, t \quad (6g)$$

$$0 \leq P_{t,i}^{Dch, DA} \leq \bar{P}_i^{Dch} v_{t,i} : \forall i, t \quad (6h)$$

$$0 \leq P_{t,i}^{Dch, UR} \leq \bar{P}_i^{Dch} v_{t,i} : \forall i, t \quad (6i)$$

$$0 \leq P_{t,i}^{Dch, DR} \leq \bar{P}_i^{Dch} v_{t,i} : \forall i, t \quad (6j)$$

2- The stored energy of BES units is calculated by (7a). According to (7b), the stored energy in BES shall be within the permissible range. Moreover, (7c) guarantees the equality of energy level at the start and end of the planning period.

$$E_{t+1,i} = E_{t,i} + P_{t,i}^{Ch} \eta_i^{Ch} - P_{t,i}^{Dch} / \eta_i^{Dch} : \forall i, t \quad (7a)$$

$$E_{t,i}^{\min} \leq E_{t,i} \leq E_{t,i}^{\max} : \forall i, t \quad (7b)$$

$$E_{0,i} = E_{T,i} : \forall i, t \quad (7c)$$

3- The generated power and heat of the CHP unit shall be within the permissible ranges, as follows:

$$P_{t,i}^{CHP} = P_{t,i}^{CHP, DA} + P_{t,i}^{CHP, UR} - P_{t,i}^{CHP, DR} : \forall i, t \quad (8a)$$

$$H_{t,i}^{CHP} = H_{t,i}^{CHP, DA} + H_{t,i}^{CHP, UR} - H_{t,i}^{CHP, DR} : \forall i, t \quad (8b)$$

$$P_i^{CHP, \min} v_{t,i} \leq P_{t,i}^{CHP} \leq P_i^{CHP, \max} v_{t,i} : \forall i, t \quad (8c)$$

$$P_i^{CHP, \min} v_{t,i} \leq P_{t,i}^{CHP, DA} \leq P_i^{CHP, \max} v_{t,i} : \forall i, t \quad (8d)$$

$$P_i^{CHP, \min} v_{t,i} \leq P_{t,i}^{CHP, UR} \leq P_i^{CHP, \max} v_{t,i} : \forall i, t \quad (8e)$$

$$P_i^{CHP, \min} v_{t,i} \leq P_{t,i}^{CHP, DR} \leq P_i^{CHP, \max} v_{t,i} : \forall i, t \quad (8f)$$

$$H_i^{CHP, \min} v_{t,i} \leq H_{t,i}^{CHP} \leq H_i^{CHP, \max} v_{t,i} : \forall i, t \quad (8g)$$

$$H_i^{CHP, \min} v_{t,i} \leq H_{t,i}^{CHP, DA} \leq H_i^{CHP, \max} v_{t,i} : \forall i, t \quad (8h)$$

$$H_i^{CHP, \min} v_{t,i} \leq H_{t,i}^{CHP, UR} \leq H_i^{CHP, \max} v_{t,i} : \forall i, t \quad (8i)$$

$$H_i^{CHP, \min} v_{t,i} \leq H_{t,i}^{CHP, DR} \leq H_i^{CHP, \max} v_{t,i} : \forall i, t \quad (8j)$$

4- The equality constraint (9a) shows the relation between temperature and heat. The hourly temperature depends on the generated heat of the CHP unit, ambient temperature, mass, and the specific heat capacity. Accordingly, the permissible interval of temperature is represented by (9b)

$$\theta_{t,i} = \frac{H_{t,i}^{CHP}}{m_i C_i^p} + \xi \theta_{t-1,i} + \theta_{t,i}^{amb} : \forall i, t \quad (9a)$$

$$\theta_{t,i}^{\min} \leq \theta_{t,i} \leq \theta_{t,i}^{\max} : \forall i, t \quad (9b)$$

5- The balances between generation and consumption in the day-ahead and regulation markets are modeled by (10a) and (10b), respectively.

$$P_{t,i}^{DA} + P_{t,i}^{CHP, DA} + P_{t,i}^{Dch, DA} - P_{t,i}^{Ch, DA} = P_{t,i}^L : \forall i, t \quad (10a)$$

$$P_{t,i}^{UR} - P_{t,i}^{DR} + P_{t,i}^{CHP, UR} - P_{t,i}^{CHP, DR} + P_{t,i}^{Dch, UR} - P_{t,i}^{Dch, DR} + P_{t,i}^{Ch, UR} - P_{t,i}^{Ch, DR} = P_{t,i}^+ - P_{t,i}^- : \forall i, t \quad (10b)$$

The stochastic model is presented in the next section.

III. CHANCE-CONSTRAINED OPTIMIZATION BASED MODEL

To evaluate impacts of uncertain consumption, $P_{t,i}^+$ and $P_{t,i}^-$ are considered as stochastic variables. In this work, different realizations of uncertain parameters are determined by the sampling approaches. According to the expected values of $P_{t,i}^+$ and $P_{t,i}^-$, and the related standard deviations, five hourly realizations are specified as follows:

$$P_{t,i}^+ = [P_{t,i}^+ - 2\sigma_{t,i}^+, P_{t,i}^+ - \sigma_{t,i}^+, P_{t,i}^+, P_{t,i}^+ + \sigma_{t,i}^+, P_{t,i}^+ + 2\sigma_{t,i}^+] : \forall i, t \quad (11a)$$

$$P_{t,i}^- = [P_{t,i}^- - 2\sigma_{t,i}^-, P_{t,i}^- - \sigma_{t,i}^-, P_{t,i}^-, P_{t,i}^- + \sigma_{t,i}^-, P_{t,i}^- + 2\sigma_{t,i}^-] : \forall i, t \quad (11b)$$

Moreover, the probability of each realization is estimated by the normal probability distribution function. The supplied regulation by EA shall be higher than the variation of consumption. In the chance-constrained approach, the risk preferences of decision-makers are controlled by the confidence level κ . Accordingly, the risk-averse and risk-taker decision-makers choose the higher and lower level of confidence level, respectively. The chance-constrained formulations in the up and down regulation markets can be represented as follows:

$$\Pr [P_{t,i}^{UR} + P_{t,i}^{CHP, UR} + P_{t,i}^{Dch, UR} + P_{t,i}^{Ch, UR} \geq P_{t,i}^+] \geq \kappa_{t,i} : \forall i, t \quad (12a)$$

$$\Pr [P_{t,i}^{DR} + P_{t,i}^{CHP, DR} + P_{t,i}^{Dch, DR} + P_{t,i}^{Ch, DR} \geq P_{t,i}^-] \geq \kappa_{t,i} : \forall i, t \quad (12b)$$

Therefore, the linear risk-based optimization problem of EA can be summarized as follow:

$$\min_{P_{t,i}^{DA}, P_{t,i}^{UR}, P_{t,i}^{DR}, P_{t,i}^{Ch}, P_{t,i}^{Dch}, v_{t,i}, P_{t,i}^{CHP}, H_{t,i}^{CHP}, \theta_{t,i} : \forall i, \forall t} \sum_{t \in T} \sum_{i \in I} C_{t,i} \quad (13)$$

$$s.t. : (1b), (2), (5) - (10), (12)$$

In the next section, the performance of the proposed model is evaluated via a case study and different scenarios.

IV. NUMERICAL RESULTS

To evaluate the performance of the proposed model, it is simulated on a case study with three groups of consumers that have different thermal requirements. The expected consumption and day-ahead prices for all groups of consumers are identical, which are presented in Fig. 3 [14]. It shall be noted that the standard deviation of price is 5% of the expected value. Moreover, it is supposed that up and down-regulation prices are equal to 1.19 and 0.95 day-ahead prices, respectively [14]. The ambient temperature and the permissible variation intervals of temperature for different consumers are shown in Fig. 4 [14]. The FOR curve of the CHP unit is demonstrated in Fig. 5.

Fig. 3. Data of consumption and day-ahead price [14].

Fig. 4. Permissible interval of temperature for different groups of consumers (C) [14].

It is supposed that all consumers are equipped with BES and CHP units. Thermal characteristics of the test system, modified data of CHP and BES units are presented in Table III [15].

Fig. 5. FOR curve of CHP unit.

To evaluate the performance of the proposed model, different case studies are considered as follows:

- Case I: The uncertainty of consumption is neglected and the optimal strategy of EA in the day-ahead market is studied.
- Case II: For the confidence level of 0.80, the impact of demand uncertainty on the optimal strategy of EA is evaluated.
- Case III: For the confidence level of 0.85, the impact of demand uncertainty on the optimal strategy of EA is evaluated.

TABLE I. DATA OF CHP AND BES UNITS, AND THERMAL CHARACTERISTICS OF THE TEST SYSTEM.

CHP			
a	0	c	0.06 Euro/kW
b	0.13 Euro/kW	d	0.0011 (Euro/kW) ²
BES			
$E^{\min/\max}$	10-180 kWh	$\eta^{CH/DCH}$	1
$P^{CH,\max}$	30 kW	ρ^B	0.01 Euro/kW
$P^{DCH,\max}$	30 kW		
Thermal characteristics of the test system			
Initial Temperature	20.5	θ	0.8
m	3675 kg	C_p	0.27917 Wh/kg-C

The optimal generated power and heat of CHP units for different groups of consumers are shown in Fig. 6. This figure shows that the CHP unit generates more heat by increasing its minimum temperature. CHP units would be more efficient if they generated both heat and electricity simultaneously. As a result, CHP's electrical power is increased by reducing the generated heat.

Fig. 6. Generated power and heat of CHP units for different groups of consumers (Case I).

As seen in Fig. 7, a higher minimum temperature increases EA's participation level on the day-ahead market. To supply the electrical demand during the high price periods, EA prefers to charge BES units during the low price periods. According to simulation results, all BES units in this case study have the same charge/discharge power as shown in Fig. 8. Moreover, the total costs for consumers 1, 2, and 3 are 421.25, 431.50, and 440.3 Euro/day, respectively.

In cases II and III, it is supposed that the variation intervals of temperature for all consumers are equal to the presented values for $i=2$ in Fig. 4. Based on the confidence level of 0.80, Fig. 9 shows EA's purchased power from the day-ahead and regulation markets, as well as the charging and discharging power of BES units.

Fig. 7. Purchased power from the day-ahead market for different groups of consumers (Case I).

Fig. 8. Energy, charging, and discharging power of BES (Case I).

Fig. 9. Optimal scheduling of resources for confidence level 0.75 (Case II).

Fig. 10. Optimal scheduling of resources for confidence level 0.85 (Case III).

The impacts of increasing the confidence level on the optimal scheduling of resources are shown in Fig. 10. A

higher confidence level means that the optimal solution is feasible in a larger number of scenarios or realizations of uncertain parameters. Fig. 10 shows the participation level of BES in the regulation service is increased from 230 to 270 kWh. Moreover, in this case, CHP units generate 82.6 kWh in the regulation service. It shall be noted that in this case, the total cost is 490.3 Euro/day.

V. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, a risk-based model is proposed for EA to schedule the flexible resources in the day-ahead and regulation markets. In the proposed model, BES and CHP units are considered as flexible resources to compensate for the variations of consumption. To linearize the cost function of CHP units, the McCormick relaxation approach is addressed. Additionally, the chance-constrained approach is used to evaluate the impacts of uncertain demand. Simulation results show that in the day-ahead market, BES could decrease the total cost by charging and discharging in low-price and high-price periods, respectively. Moreover, considering the uncertainty of consumption increases the participation level of BES and CHP units in the regulation service. However, these values are highly affected by the confidence level. The presented results indicate that increasing the confidence level from 0.80 to 0.85 leads to an increase of 17.4% in the traded power of BES in the regulation service and a 5.4% increase in the cost of EA.

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